

Properties of Concrete using Plastic Scrap a Review

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Micro cracks in concrete are formed during its hardening stage. A discontinuous heterogeneous system exists even before the application of any external load. When the load is applied, micro cracks start developing along the planes, which may experience relatively low tensile strains, at about 25-30% of the ultimate strength in compression. Further application of the load leads to uncontrolled growth of micro cracks. The low resistance to tensile crack propagation in turn results in a low fracture toughness, and limited resistance to impact and explosive loading.

The low tensile strength of concrete is being compensated in several ways, and this has been achieved by the use of reinforcing bars and also by applying pre-stressing force. Though these methods provide tensile strength to concrete, they do not increase the inherent tensile strength of concrete itself.

These deficiencies have led researchers to investigate and develop a material, which could perform better in areas where conventional concrete has several limitations. One such development has been two phase composite materials i.e., fibre reinforced concrete, in which cement based matrix is reinforced with ordered or random distribution of fibres. Fibres in the cement based matrix acts as cracks arrester, which restricts the growth of flaws in the matrix, preventing these from enlarging under load, into cracks, which eventually cause failure. Prevention of propagation of cracks originating from internal flaws can result in improvements in static and dynamic properties of the matrix.

INTRODUCTION

The plain cement concrete has very low tensile strength, restricted pliability, and little protection from breaking. Inward miniaturized scale breaks are innately present in the concrete and its poor rigidity is because of the proliferation of such small cracks, in the long run prompting fragile disappointment of the concrete. The most generally acknowledged solution for this flexural shortcoming of cement is the regular fortification with high quality steel. Regardless of the way that these procedures offer flexibility to people, they however don't grow the trademark unbending nature of solid itself. In like manner the help putting and profitable compaction of RCC is amazingly troublesome if the solid is of low workability especially by virtue of overpowering solid (M-30). In plain concrete and near feeble materials, assistant parts (scaled down scale breaks) become even before stacking, particularly on account of drying shrinkage or distinctive purposes behind volume change. The width of these breaks on occasion outperforms a few microns, yet their two estimations may be of higher enormity.

Concrete is the most widely used construction material. Because of its specialty of being cast in any desirable shape, it has replaced stone and brick masonry. Plain concrete is weak in tension and has limited ductility and little resistance to cracking. Micro cracks are present in concrete because of its poor tensile strength. The cracks propagate with the application of load, leading to brittle fracture of concrete.

Plastic Fibre Reinforced Concrete

Enhancing the tensile properties of plain concrete numerous strategies have been developed. A considerable lot of the strategies prevailing with regards to making the concrete individuals impervious to strain, however none of them expanded the inborn tractable properties of plain concrete. The scattering of strands in concrete network to enhance its ductile properties has been drilled worldwide more than 3 past decades. The expansion of little firmly separated and consistently scattered filaments to cement would go about as break arrester and would considerably enhance its static and dynamic properties. This sort of concrete is known as fibre reinforced concrete. Fibre strengthened concrete can be characterized as a composite material comprising of blends of bond, mortar, or concrete and broken, discrete, consistently scattered appropriate strands. Consistent lattices, woven textures and long wires or poles are not thought to be discrete fibres.

Fibres Used

The waste plastic fibres were obtained by cutting waste plastic pots, buckets, cans, drums and utensils. The waste plastic fibres obtained were all recycled plastics. The fibres were cut from steel wire cutter and it is labour oriented. The thickness of waste plastic fibres was 1mm and its breadth was kept 5mm and these fibres were straight. The different volume fraction of fibres and suitable aspect ratio were selected and used in this investigation

Literature Survey

General

In this section an elaborative talk is made with respect to works done as such far around there as writing audit. Fibre strengthened cement with Fibres scraps and their conduct contemplates are talked about in short

[1] B Jaivignesh, 2018

Disposal of large quantity of plastic causes land, water and air pollution etc., so a study is conducted to recycle the plastic in concrete. This work investigates about the replacement of natural aggregate with non-biodegradable plastic aggregate made up of mixed plastic waste in concrete. Several tests are conducted such as compressive strength of cube, split tensile strength of cylinder, flexural strength test of prism to identify the properties and behavior of concrete using plastic aggregate. Replacement of fine aggregate weight by 10%, 15%, 20% with Plastic fine (PF) aggregate and for each replacement of fine aggregate 15%, 20%, 25% of coarse aggregate replacement also conducted with Plastic Coarse(PC) aggregate. In literatures reported that the addition of plastic aggregate in concrete causes the reduction of strength in concrete due to poor bonding between concrete and plastic aggregate, so addition of 0.3% of steel fiber by weight of cement in concrete is done to improve the concrete strength. Totally 60 cubes, 60 cylinders and 40 prisms are casted to identify the compressive strength, split tensile strength and flexural strength respectively. Casted specimens are tested at 7 and 28 days. The identified results from concrete using plastic aggregate are compared with conventional concrete. Result shows that reduction in mechanical properties of plastic aggregate added concrete. This reduction in strength is mainly due to poor bond strength between cement and plastic aggregate..

[2] Aswani Sabu and Thomas Paul, 2017

Fibers are generally used as a common engineering material for crack resistance and strengthening of concrete. Their properties and characteristics greatly influence the properties of concrete which has been proved already in many previous researches. Accordingly it has been found that steel fibers give the maximum strength in comparison to glass and polypropylene fibers. In this experimental study, two types of steel fibers namely hooked end and crimped fibers are used. The volume fractions taken are 0.75%, 1.0% and 1.25% and M30 grade concrete is adopted. Cement has been replaced with 25% of Class F flash. The primary focus is to compare the mechanical properties of concrete using both fibres.

[3] R. Madheswaran, S. Arun Singh, K.S Sathyanarayanan 2015

Concrete is likely the most broadly utilized development material on the planet. The primary fixing in the regular cement is Portland concrete. The measure of bond generation produces around rise to measure of carbon dioxide into the climate. Concrete creation is devouring noteworthy measure of characteristic assets. That has brought weights to lessen bond utilization by the utilization of supplementary materials. Accessibility of mineral admixtures checked opening of another period for planning solid blend of ever more elevated quality. Fly Ash and silica smolder is another mineral admixture, whose potential isn't completely used. Also just restricted investigations have been completed in India on the utilization of silica smolder for the improvement of high quality cement with expansion

of steel strands. The examination centers around the compressive quality execution of the mixed cement containing diverse level of silica smoke and Fly Ash and steel fiber as an incomplete substitution of OPC. The bond in concrete is supplanted as needs be with Silica seethe content was use from 0% to 10% in the interim of 2% in weight premise and furthermore fly cinder content was use from 10% in weight premise. So to enhance the quality of solid steel filaments were included 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, 2% by weight of steel fiber. Solid 3D shapes are tried at the age of 3, 7, and 28 days of curing. At last, the quality execution of Fly slag and silica rage mixed fiber fortified cement is contrasted and the execution of customary cement. From the exploratory examinations, it has been watched that, the ideal substitution Fly fiery remains and silica smoke to bond and steel fiber without changing much the compressive quality is 10% - 8 % and 1.5 % individually for M30 review Concrete

[4] Hoe Kwan Mahyuddin Ramli, 2016

Notwithstanding being presented to chloride and sulfate assaults, marine structures are liable to seismic and affect loads coming about because of waves, affect with strong protests, and water transports. Accordingly, the flexural conduct and effect protection of Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (FRC) in marine condition must be clarified. Nonetheless, such data is barely announced. Along these lines, this examination plans to investigate the impacts of mimicked forceful conditions on flexural quality and effect protection of FRC and to recognize the connection between the two parameters. Three sorts of filaments, specifically, coconut fiber, Barsrap fiber (BF), and soluble base safe glass fiber, were utilized as a part of this investigation. The fiber measurements extended from 0.6% to 2.4% of the cover volume. All blends have consistent water/folio proportion of 0.37 and their compressive qualities were all surpassing 60 MPa. The examples were arranged and presented to three diverse forceful presentation situations, in particular, tropical atmosphere, cyclic air and seawater conditions, and seawater condition for up to 180 days. Results demonstrate that flexural quality and effect protection of FRC have an immediate association with fiber content. Regardless, change in fiber write is more critical than expanding fiber dose in improving flexural quality yet modification in the two issues would fundamentally affect the effect protection. Rigidity of an individual BF (640 MPa) is significantly higher than the flexural quality of the BFRC composite. Along these lines, disappointment of solid lattice was seen to happen preceding the crack of the fiber which thusly brought about fiber haul out from the solid grid. Among the different FRC analyzed, FRC containing the most elevated BF content (2.4%) exhibited the best flexural quality execution. The flexural quality of the Bar srup FRC was seen to be expanded by 11- 13% in all presentation situations following 180 days. The pre-break vitality ingestions, which were resolved through effect stack test, were found to increment by 60- 63% when contrasted with the control solid, which showed no post-split vitality assimilation. In the interim, the post-break vitality retentions of the 2.4BF were found to go between 3.67 J and 3.71 J for different ecological introduction conditions. Examination of fluctuation (ANOVA) comes about demonstrated that flexural qualities were fundamentally expanded following a half year of presentation to the different forceful condition conditions, particularly in seawater. This could be because of arrangement of salt gems which contributed towards improving the fiber/lattice frictional bond. Notwithstanding,

the presentation situations have no noteworthy impact on affect protection execution.

[5] Su-Jin Lee, 2015

In this investigation, basic nano-engineered and steel filaments were utilized to lessen the measure of steel rebar appropriated in precast fortified solid composite individuals. The flexural execution of the individuals was assessed utilizing longitudinal steel proportions of 1.65 and 1.20 and a transverse steel proportion of 0.20. Cross breed fiber blends comprising of different measures of auxiliary nano-manufactured and snared end steel filaments were utilized as fortifying materials alongside the steel rebar. The nano-manufactured fiber volume parts were 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6 vol. %, and the steel fiber substance were 5, 10, and 20 kg/m³. Flexural execution tests were completed for the subsequent half breed fiber-strengthened bond composites. The test outcomes exhibited that the half breed fiber-fortified concrete composites fulfilled the essential conditions to supplant the general strengthening bars as per the RILEM standard when the blend contained 0.4 vol. % of nano-manufactured fiber and 20 kg/m³ of steel fiber. The flexural conduct of a 350 * 180 * 1500-mm precast composite part fortified by such a half and half fiber blend and steel rebar was assessed; its most extreme load was 30% more noteworthy than the outlined extreme load and 3.5% more prominent than that of a steel fiber-strengthened composite part. The material execution of cement with a half and half blend of fortifying basic nano-engineered and steel filaments was assessed. The best blend was then tried in a precast RC composite part utilizing the most reduced conceivable steel proportion to assess the flexural execution.

[6] Lijun Wang, Jing Zhang, Xu Yang, Chun Zhang, 2016

Epoxy syntactic froths containing 15 wt.% empty glass smaller scale expand were strengthened by fiberglass work as well as short glass fiber, and the flexural conduct of these froths were examined. Flexural tests comes about demonstrated that the nearness of glass fiber or fiberglass work prompted expanded estimations of quality and modulus in syntactic froths contrasted and unreinforced syntactic froths. Furthermore, fiberglass work was observed to be considerably more productive. By adding two-layer fiberglass work to the glass fiber fortified syntactic froths, the flexural quality and modulus additionally expanded just about 2.5 and 2 times, individually, while the thickness of the strengthened froth just expanded by 9.3%. Moreover, it was discovered that the position and layers of fiberglass work had huge impact of the flexural properties. The disappointment modes and instruments of various fortified syntactic froths are inspected and the basic contrasts are talked about. Flexural properties of strengthened syntactic froths are explored in this examination. Fiberglass work and additionally short glass fiber stirred as support to get three arrangement of composites. Results demonstrate that the flexural properties are improved by the nearness of glass fiber or fiberglass work and fiberglass work is observed to be significantly more proficient. The flexural quality and modulus expanded by 28% and 19%, individually, for the fiber-fortified syntactic froths as for that of the unreinforced syntactic froths. Be that as it may, the expansion of one-layer fiberglass work created an essential change in flexural quality and modulus (165% and 38%, individually) contrasted and unreinforced froth, when the area of the fiberglass work was far from the pressure surface ($x/h = 1$).

Syntactic froths strengthened by 0.5 wt.% glass fiber and two-layer fiberglass work demonstrated 2.8 and 2.4 times higher flexural quality and modulus than that of the plain syntactic froths while the thickness of fortified froth just expanded by 9.3%. The crack surface demonstrated that the impact of area of work on the flexural properties was because of various disappointment components. Amid flexure, the fiberglass work on the tractable side can stop the small scale breaks engendering while the arbitrarily scattered short glass strands can connect splits at short interims and diminish their spread rate. Hypothetical investigation indicated assist improvement in flexural quality might be accomplished by enhancing the interface bond between fiber work and polymer lattice.

Problem identification

- Plastic Fiber Waste hinder and control the arrangement of characteristic splitting in solid, subsequently guaranteeing a more strong solid development.
- Plastic Fiber Waste enhance the protection from shattering powers caused because of seismic tremor chaps, in this way making concrete a more adaptable material for basic applications .
- Through Literature survey it was found the work on different scraps material individually have been done, No information are available on combination of scraps material for M-30 Grade of Concrete.
- Need for handling & proper utilization of scrap material.
- Alternative substitute materials of concrete as replacement are not known.

Objectives

The objectives of the research are outlined below:

- To study properties of Plastic Fiber reinforced concrete.
- To study the strength of concrete by partial replacement of coarse aggregate using plastic fiber.
- To study the workability of concrete prepared by partial replacement of coarse aggregate using plastic fiber.

CONCLUSION

Compressive, Tensile and flexural quality is expanding on expanding the level of Plastic Fiber Scrap.

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